

RADiation harvesting of bioactive peptides from egg **prO**teins and their integration in ad**V**anced functional products

INNOVATION ACTION OF HORIZON EUROPE EURATOM RESEARCH AND TRAINING
PROGRAMME GA N° 101061694

DELIVERABLE REPORT

Plan for Communication and Dissemination

DELIVERABLE: D5.3

Document identifier:	RADOV-Del-D5.3
Due date of deliverable:	End of month 20 (April 2024)
Report release date:	20/05/2024
Work package:	WP5 [Plan for Communication and Dissemination]
Lead beneficiary:	HUD
Document status:	Final

ABSTRACT

The RADOV Communication and Dissemination Plan has been developed within the overall RADOV Communication Strategy following the basic objectives drafted in the RADOV proposal. It defines the RADOV communication and dissemination strategy and plans for how this will be delivered. This is the first scheduled update of the plan. As the last version of the original plan is recent, the main change is the inclusion of the communication and dissemination activities undertaken and the plans for future activities.

Funded by
the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe Research and Training programme under Grant Agreement No 101061694.

RADOV began in September 2022 and will run for 4 years.

Delivery Slip

	Name		Partner	Date
Authored by	Rob Edgecock		HUD	16/05/2024
Edited by	Rob Edgecock		HUD	16/05/2024
Reviewed by	Dagmara Chmielewska-Śmietanko		INCT	20/05/2024
Approved by	Dagmara Chmielewska-Śmietanko		INCT	20/05/2024

Change Log

Version	Date	Amended by	Changes
v.1.0	16/05/2024	HUD	First draft
v.2.0	20/05/2024	INCT	Final formatting

Version Management

Reviewed by	All Partners
Approved by	All Partners
Authorized by	Coordinator, Dagmara Chmielewska-Śmietanko

(1) Introduction

The dissemination and exploitation of results are of great importance in RADOV. All Partners are committed to communicating and disseminating the results developed in the project. The identified target groups of such activities are:

- a) the research community in the field of radiation processing
- b) large companies and SMEs from the radiation processing and egg product industries
- c) large companies and SMEs from the food, pharma, packaging, biotechnology and nutraceutical sectors
- d) public institutions and policy makers at national, European and worldwide level
- e) the general public.

Continuous communication activities will be undertaken, using a language easily understandable by non-specialists, to enhance the overall project visibility. This will ultimately also maximize the valorisation and exploitation of the project's results. Communication will contribute in a clear synergistic way with the dissemination activities to engage stakeholder groups during the whole project life and ensure the results respond to their needs and expectations.

The initial Communication and Dissemination Plan was described previously. This document will give a first update, with a focus on the communication and dissemination activities undertaken in the first 20 months of RADOV and those planned for the future.

(2) Communication and Dissemination Strategy

The RADOV strategy for communication and dissemination is to ensure that the knowledge produced during the project is quickly and efficiently communicated to all consortium partners and any external stakeholders who may be interested in our results. The specific stakeholders and the communication methods are described below. The dissemination to external stakeholders will be done as promptly as possible, while allowing time for the consortium to fully exploit the results. All exploitable results and data will be stored on a long-term platform to allow their use once the project is complete.

All publications and data will, by the end of the project, be stored open access and open data and will fully comply with the FAIR principles.

2.1 Objectives

The RADOV overall communication goals are to:

1. Implement efficient knowledge sharing among the project participants.
2. Engage the wider scientific community with the project developments;
3. Facilitate the knowledge transfer between this project and industry working in this and related areas;
4. Engage the public with the potential of bioactive peptides and their applications;

5. Demonstrate the impact of the project to the public and policy-makers;
6. Demonstrate the project is on track and its objectives are achieved.

The main objectives of RADOV regarding our dissemination plans are to:

1. provide timely information about our scientific results;
2. facilitate the communication of publications of our scientific results to EU, scientists, industry and other potential users of the results;
3. provide a platform, which incorporates the requirements of Open Access and Open Data, ensuring that readers are granted access to our scientific output without financial, legal or technical barriers;
4. provide a platform which respects the requirements of the FAIR principles and modern publishing procedures and tools.

To achieve these goals, the project overall dissemination and communication strategy is implementing the activities below. The activities already undertaken or planned are given in Section 5.

1. Setting up and continuous updating of a dedicated project website and of web-pages on partners' web-sites (M1-M48): Each web page will display information about the project aims and objectives, its partners and the Horizon Europe and Euratom Programmes. Moreover, the dedicated website will give visibility to the project and collect and present ongoing activities and results of the project.

2. Project events (M1-M48). RADOV will hold 2 innovation workshops to engage with industry and potential end users. These will be targeted at possible manufacturers and users of these products, the scientific community working on the applications of ionizing radiation and companies interested in polymer processing. It is planned to hold the first of these online, to attract the largest possible audience, in M36. This will give an introduction to the project and the benefit the results could bring. Our aim is for an attendance of around 25. The remaining workshop will be held in person in M47 to allow the attendees to see the products themselves, how they are manufactured and what the potential is and to discuss the next steps. Participants from the online workshop and others who may be interested will be invited and we aim for an attendance of 30.

3. Participation in events external to the consortium (M6-M48). Participation of consortium members in external events of relevance for dissemination purposes (for example key conferences and significant universities conferences, industrial fairs and exhibitions in the field of nuclear science, technology and related industries that make extensive use of ionising radiation, such as pharma, egg products, food, packaging and nutraceuticals) is planned. In particular, consortium members will present RADOV results at the most important international conferences in the field of ionizing radiation application. This includes the Miller Conference on Radiation Chemistry (June 2023), the International Conference on Development and Applications of Nuclear Technologies NUTECH (September 2023), the International Conference on Applications of Radiation Science and Technology (August 2022, April 2025) and the International Conference on Ionizing Processes ICIP (August 2024). RADOV will also

be present at the exhibition organized in conjunction with the ICARST 2025 Conference. This will give the opportunity to present solutions and products developed within RADOV to the approximately 600 participants from IAEA Member States and international organizations.

RADOV will be also present at selected IAEA meetings organized in the frame of Technical Cooperation Projects (e.g. RER1024 "Enhancing the Use of Radiation Technologies for Improved Resource Efficiency").

4. Liaison activities (M1-48): the consortium will liaise with international, EU, national, regional projects on the same, or similar, issues, thus contributing to mainstreaming the developed results. The RADOV consortium will perform extensive liaison activities with existing projects related to Horizon Europe and the Euratom programme and to nuclear technology, whose results might be of relevance to better tailor its activities, particularly to guarantee the market uptake of selected applications and products. The RADOV scope will be presented at the several events related to the IFAST project. The opportunities created by the EURO-Labs project that provides the access to the available resources to a large fraction of EUROpean Laboratories for Accelerator Based Sciences (EURO-LABS) will be used to broaden the scope of experiments planned in RADOV.

5. Publications (M6-M48): scientific articles related to methodology developments and results will be published. Articles for the scientific and engineering communities will be published in high impact factor, Open Access, international peer-reviewed journals, using both the green and gold models for the publication of the results. Also, an open repository, Zenodo, will be used for publishing working papers. The journals will be selected based on their subject material, but given the importance of this work, we will consider publication of the results in a Nature journal. As the project presents multidisciplinary approach leading journals in radiation chemistry, bioactive substances and polymer science will be selected to disseminate the results. Nevertheless, as there are a number of high-ranked journals offering the publication opportunity in the mentioned above fields the final choice will depend on the scope of the publication.

Scientific articles for the general public will be prepared by HUD and made available through electronic means to all the partners and organisations the consortium has links with.

6. Press releases, social media and other mass media relations (M1-M48): project information will be disseminated also through social media and mass media. The main social medium to be used will be LinkedIn and a RADOV page has already been created and is being used. Information on project events and work progress will be posted on the RADOV and the Partner Institutions' webpages. Further dissemination will be undertaken using the Accelerating News newsletter (see below) and the INCT Facebook fanpage. Reports on RADOV events will be published regularly in Progress in Nuclear Technology.

One of the main aims of the RADOV dissemination plan is to setup efficient procedures and modern dynamic tools, promoting and facilitating collaborative work, following up the life-cycle of documents in an interactive clear way, from its initial development stages to final publication. The aim is to delegate to the Work Package Coordinators the responsibility to make available the final approved versions to the broader scientific

communities, and the public at large, using the RADOV publication procedures and tools (see Annex 1). The Coordinators will be supported in this task by the dedicated Work Package responsible for Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation (WP5). With the aim of facilitating the process of open access publication, this plan also includes setting up and testing of procedures and associated tools as well as the preparation of explicit guidelines for the RADOV collaborators.

2.2 Target Audiences

The RADOV partners are committed to communicating and disseminating the results developed in the project, from the very beginning. The target audiences include the scientific community, industry working both in radiation processing and the application areas of our work, other potential users, policy-makers, the EU and the general public.

A summary of the different audiences, the related communication needs and information, the appropriate channels and expected outcomes is presented in the table below. The RADOV communication team is creating content that is fit for multiple channels and audiences. In addition, specific communication activities are being designed to reach specific audiences including the project’s participants, industry and wider communities that are the primary targets of the dissemination plan.

Audience	Information needs	Drivers	Channels/ Platforms	Outcome
Project participants	Project information; updates on work plan implementation (events, results), outreach materials	Community spirit; career development	Website, mailing lists, project meetings	Engagement with project results; sense of pride
Wider scientific community	Main advancements in the science; opportunities to collaborate	Scientific excellence; peer recognition; funding	Newsletter <i>Accelerating News</i> ; beneficiaries’ and projects’ channels; community events; LinkedIn; website	Identifying common challenges, knowledge sharing, closer collaborations
European Industry	Academic publications, potential knowledge-transfer opportunities,	Innovation; job creation; collaboration	Dedicated Industry events organised by RADOV; beneficiaries’ channels; LinkedIn; website	Knowledge and technology transfer, joint R&D
Funding agencies & decision-makers	Summary of results; project impact; policy recommendations	Scientific excellence; economic and societal impact	Website, newsletter <i>Accelerating News</i> , marketing material (e.g. brochure); LinkedIn; website	Support to project community; demonstration of return of investment in accelerator S&T

Public	Impact of the applications	Curiosity, societal impact	Social media, including the beneficiaries’ channels; public talks; LinkedIn	Support for fundamental research
---------------	----------------------------	----------------------------	---	----------------------------------

2.3 Open Access Policy and Intellectual Property Rights

The RADOV Communication and Dissemination plan of scientific results follows the Horizon Europe directives and is based on the principles of Open Access. As a first step, it includes the exploration of different options and the recommendation of appropriate open access platforms that implement the FAIR principles so that the data are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable.

The plan is shaped following the EU relevant guidelines, in order to ensure that readers are granted access to the RADOV scientific output without financial, legal or technical barriers. We plan to follow both the “Gold Open Access” and the “Green Open Access” promoting open access publishing and self-archiving respectively (see Section 3.2). Accordingly, the RADOV Publications Guidelines (see Annex 1) summarise the main points facilitating the publication process and ensuring that such requirements are implemented. It is clearly stated that each beneficiary must ensure open access to peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to results according to the project’s Grant Agreement.

It is also clarified that Open Access is not a requirement to publish and researchers are free to decide whether to publish or not. Open access does not affect the decision to exploit research results commercially (e.g., through patenting). Therefore, the decision to publish through open access comes after the more general decision on whether to publish directly or to first seek protection of Intellectual Property Rights.

Intellectual Property Rights

In general, the principles for dissemination, access and use of results generated through RADOV fully comply with the requirements of Horizon Europe and Euratom. Access to Results and Background and ownership of results follows the principles set out in the Grant Agreement. Furthermore, the Consortium Agreement defines the procedures for publication, taking into account the potential for commercial exploitation and/or the need for protection of Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) of the concerned results, with due consideration of the IPR practices of all participants. Indeed, RADOV aims at implementing efficient management of IPR, which is essential for successfully exploiting the research results of the project and for protecting the interests of the institutes and companies that have produced these results.

It is expected that some of the main exploitable RADOV results will have a wider impact beyond the specific project targets and objectives. Since these will constitute the RADOV “flagship results” they will be disseminated to larger scientific and public audiences.

(3) RADOV Communication and Dissemination Methods

3.1 OVERVIEW

In order to achieve the set objectives, and address the information needs of the target audiences the RADOV Communication and Dissemination plan consists of setting up and using the following basic channels and platforms for dissemination of its scientific results:

- Web page and its linked communications channels and documents repository;
- Zenodo repository for the Open Access storage of publications and the Open Data storage of data
- the use of Indico for the organisation of meetings and the storage of related material:
 - Conferences and workshops
 - Network events
 - Project meetings (in-person or online)
 - public outreach events;
- Scientific Journal publications
- The use of LinkedIn for the communication of RADOV and other related events and for the dissemination of RADOV results to a potentially broad audience
- Open Research Europe
 - Accelerating News online Bulletin
 - News items on significant progress

3.2 DISSEMINATION TOOLS

In addition to publishing in scientific journals, different opportunities for immediate dissemination of results to the scientific communities are foreseen through presentations at conferences, organisation of open workshops or network events but also communication to the scientific communities via newsletters and bulletins. Proper archiving of all these kinds of documents, ensuring their accessibility, is of paramount importance and set the requirements for the development and implementation of the RADOV dissemination and communication plan and tools.

Project website: As part of its overall dissemination and communication plan, RADOV provides information about its activities and results, foremost and most importantly, among all RADOV members. Naturally, the primary tool for dissemination and communication is the project's website which acts as central information hub and is the gateway to different information channels and/or platforms including news and announcements, upcoming events, newsletters, publications, among others. Through the RADOV web site announcements of upcoming events are posted including major conferences where RADOV participants are encouraged to present their scientific results.

The RADOV web page (<https://RADOV.eu>) is set up as a central information hub; it also links to the RADOV internal communication intranet, with restricted access to RADOV members only. While the RADOV web page is used for the dissemination of results to the scientific communities and communication to general public, the internal communication space is designated to the Members and Partners of the RADOV community and tailored to their needs, primarily, for the development of documents and efficient flow of information. Documents are stored in the Zenodo repository, with restricted access while being developed, but open access to the final versions. This is available via the RADOV web page.

In the editorial process and life-cycle of documents the Work Package Coordinators and Task Leaders play a key role. Documents are developed internally, under their supervision and requiring their approval. They make sure that documents, after their final approval, become available externally, which is the key point for dissemination to broader scientific and other communities. They are responsible for submitting the (a) final published versions of scientific publications to the RADOV Zenodo repository and (b) the EU contractual documents, such as deliverables and milestones, to the RADOV project management team that then submits them to the EU portal. The final versions of these documents are also stored in the RADOV repository.

ZENODO REPOSITORY: After reviewing the experiences on tools and procedures implemented for previous EU projects such as ARIES and EuCARD and investigating different available options, Zenodo was chosen as the appropriate repository for all RADOV publications. Zenodo is an open repository (<http://zenodo.org>) which provides a common platform for Open Access to Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe results across various scientific fields and is integrated into reporting lines for research funded by the European Commission via OpenAIRE (<http://openaire.eu>). Hence, the “Green” standard in RADOV takes the form of self-archiving in Zenodo all RADOV publications including journal publications; conference and workshop papers; scientific and technical notes and reports; academic dissertations; posters; presentations; handouts and flyers; and press articles.

Since reporting documents stored in Zenodo are being picked up by the EU portal, making documents available via Zenodo also establishes a convenient and straightforward reporting link.

The RADOV dissemination plan consciously subscribes to the FAIR principles and easily adopted them since the Zenodo principles are compatible with FAIR principles as summarised in the Zenodo dedicated web page <https://about.zenodo.org/principles/>.

As well as meeting the EU requirements for Open Access, Zenodo also meets the requirements for Open Data. As a result, RADOV will also store data, in particular that used in publications, in Zenodo and will ensure that all the Open Data requirements are met.

The RADOV dedicated “community space” in Zenodo has been created and is accessible, and ready for use, under the link:

<https://zenodo.org/communities/radov/?page=1&size=20>

Indico: RADOV will also use the Indico tool for organising meetings. This has been installed in HUD and is linked to the RADOV website.

Indico is a tool created by CERN which enables the arrangement of meetings of all sizes, from very small up to major conferences. It helps with the organisation of events from the beginning. This includes registration and abstract submission, if required, to the presentation and storage of conference materials, which are made available to participants from the event web page, with any appropriate protections.

RADOV will employ Indico for all relevant meetings and events.

Accelerating News: This is a well-established quarterly electronic newsletter which reaches a community of 1500 subscribers (<https://acceleratingnews.web.cern.ch/>). RADOV members will be encouraged to subscribe and to become active contributors of the newsletters disseminating their RADOV activities. Important results will also be publicised by this route, as well as the others already discussed. In addition, RADOV has close links with two other important organisations working in the field of radiation processing, the International Atomic Energy Authority (IAEA) and the International Irradiation Association (iia). The results of the project will also be reported through those organisations to reach an even wider audience.

LinkedIn: This is widely used in industry and has over 1 billion registered users. It is a very good method for spreading information, though initial work is required to create a network. A RADOV account has been created and work has started on creating a network and linking our account with others working in similar areas. This will continue for the duration of the project and beyond

3.3 EVALUATION AND FUTURE IMPROVEMENTS

During the early stages of the project, the majority of the published documents will be mostly reporting documents, deliverables and milestones. As the work of RADOV advances, publications of scientific results are expected to increase; those are going to provide the basis for further dissemination to broader communities, including policy-makers and the public. Currently the feedback of the RADOV collaborators on the communication and dissemination tools is positive, while further evaluations are planned. Based on this and further input from other users, further changes to this plan will be documented in an update in M30.

4 Communication and Dissemination Activities

The following communication and dissemination activities have been undertaken or are already planned for the rest of the project. A comparison with the expectations in the summary table from the first version of the plan is given at the end of this section.

PUBLICATIONS

1. Picone, P.; Sanfilippo, T.; Vasto, S.; Baldassano, S.; Guggino, R.; Nuzzo, D.; Bulone, D.; San Biagio, P.L.; Muscolino, E.; Monastero, R.; Dispenza, C.; Giacomazza, D.. From Small Peptides to Large Proteins against Alzheimer's Disease. *Biomolecules* 2022, 12, 1344. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biom12101344>

PLANNED

1. Publication by IST-ID team on bioactivity results of the protein powders.
2. Publication by IST-ID team on bioactivity results of protein solutions.
3. Publication by Marta Walo on packaging foil grafting

4. Publication by KTH on reductive fragmentation of proteins

LIST OF THE DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

DELIVERED

Dissemination activity name	Date and Place	What? Type of dissemination activity	Who? Target audience	Why?	Status
Oral presentation by Clelia Dispenza at the 32nd Miller Conference on Radiation Chemistry with title <i>Expanding 3D bioprinting capabilities for tissue engineering using radiation engineered biopolymers</i>	3-8 June 2023 Furani (Corsica, France)	Top 5 International conferences on Radiation Chemistry and Radiation Processing	Scientists	To demonstrate to the scientific community the opportunities offered by the combination of two technologies, 3D printing and radiation processing, in regenerative medicine, including wound management	Delivered
Poster presentation by Federica Gulino at the 32nd Miller Conference on Radiation Chemistry with title <i>Radiation Crosslinked Advanced Wound Dressing Containing Egg White Proteins</i>	3-8 June 2023 Furani (Corsica, France)	Top 5 International conferences on Radiation Chemistry and radiation processing	Scientists	To share with the scientific community of radiation chemists and technologists the preliminary results of WP3 activities toward the development of advanced hydrogel wound dressings	Delivered
Poster presentation by Clelia Dispenza at XIII Congresso Nazionale AICIng – Il Congresso Nazionale della Divisione di Chimica per le	25-28 June 2023 Milan	National Conference	Scientists	To present the scope of RADOV project	Delivered

Tecnologie della Società Chimica Italiana with title <i>Novel functional biomaterials from egg white protein irradiation</i>					
Poster presentation by Urszula Gryczka at the International Conference on Development and Applications of Nuclear Technologies (NUTECH2023) with title <i>Optimization of eb irradiation parameters for functionalization of food packaging films</i>	20-22 September 2023 Cracow	Top 5 International conferences on Radiation Chemistry and Radiation Processing	Scientists	Demonstration of the ionizing radiation application to obtain packaging films with improved bioactive properties and the development of a new product.	Delivered
Oral presentation by Felicia Karlahag at the 32nd Miller Conference on Radiation Chemistry with title <i>Radiation-Induced Protein Fragmentation</i>	3-8 June 2023 Furani (Corsica, France)	Top 5 International conferences on Radiation Chemistry and Radiation Processing	Scientists	To share with the scientific community of radiation chemists results of WP2 activities toward the radiation-induced fragmentation of hen egg proteins. Results will be further base for the D2.1.	Delivered
Invited lecture by Dagmara Chmielewska-Śmietanko at the Second International Conference on	22-26 August 2023, Vienna	Top 5 International conferences on Radiation Chemistry and	Scientists, Industry, Innovators,	Lecture "The legacy of Maria Skłodowska-Curie on the role of women in nuclear science - INCT	Delivered

Applications of Radiation Science and Technology (ICARST-2022) with the title <i>The legacy of Maria Skłodowska-Curie on the role of women in nuclear science - INCT as an example</i>		Radiation Processing	International organizations (IAEA, WIN)	as an example" presenting the role of women in the RADOV project.	
Presentation by Joana Madureira with title Effect of electron beam radiation on the bioactive properties of egg proteins	30 November 2023, Bobadela (Portugal)	Workshop Earth Systems, Radioactivity and Cultural Heritage ESRCH, Centro de Ciências e Tecnologias Nucleares, Instituto Superior Técnico, Universidade de Lisboa	Students, Scientists,	To present the scope of RADOV project.	Delivered
Invited lecture by Dagmara Chmielewska-Śmietanko at the 12 th European Young Engineers Conference (EYEC 2024) with the title <i>Ionizing radiation as the tool for engineering</i>	15-17 April 2024, Warsaw	International Conference	Students, Scientists, Industry.	To present the scope of RADOV project as the one of the opportunities of ionizing radiation use in engineering.	Delivered

PLANNED

Dissemination activity name	Date and Place	What? Type of dissemination activity	Who? Target audience	Why?	Status

<p>Oral communication by Federica Gulino at BIC 2024 9th INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON INDUSTRIAL BIOTECHNOLOGY with title <i>Radiation Crosslinked Hydrogels With Egg White Proteins For Wound Healing</i></p>	<p>30 June -3 July 2024 Bologna</p>	<p>International Conference</p>	<p>Scientists</p>	<p>To present the progress of WP3 activities toward the development of advanced hydrogel wound dressings to the community of biotechnologists</p>	<p>Planned</p>
<p>Oral communication by Federica Gulino at SCI 2024 ELEMENTS OF FUTURE XXVIII National Congress of Società Chimica Italiana, with title <i>Radiation crosslinked hydrogel wound dressings containing egg white proteins</i></p>	<p>26 - 30 August 2024 Milan</p>	<p>National Congress</p>	<p>Scientists</p>	<p>To present the progress of WP3 activities toward the development of advanced hydrogel wound dressings to the Italian community of chemists and chemical technologists.</p>	<p>Planned</p>
<p>Oral communication by Clelia Dispenza at 4th International Conference on Ionizing Processes (ICIP 2024) with the title <i>Radiation driven transformation of egg white proteins and their integration of new functional bio and nanomaterials</i></p>	<p>11-15 August 2024 Notre Dame (USA)</p>	<p>Top 5 International conferences on Radiation Chemistry and Radiation processing</p>	<p>Scientists</p>	<p>To demonstrate to the potential of radiation chemistry of egg white proteins to generate novel and/or advanced functional (nano) materials.</p>	<p>Planned</p>
<p>Oral presentation by IST-ID team at Third International Conference on Applications of Radiation Science</p>	<p>7-11 April 2024 Vienna</p>	<p>Top 5 International conferences on Radiation Chemistry and</p>	<p>Scientists, Industry, Innovators,</p>	<p>To demonstrate the bioactivity results</p>	<p>Planned</p>

and Technology (ICARST-2025)		Radiation processing	International organizations (IAEA, WIN)		
Presentation by Marta Walo at Third International Conference on Applications of Radiation Science and Technology (ICARST-2025)	7-11 April 2024 Vienna	Top 5 International conferences on Radiation Chemistry and Radiation processing	Scientists, Industry, Innovators, International organizations (IAEA, WIN)	To demonstrate the packaging foil grafting	Planned

LIST OF THE COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

DELIVERED

Communication activity name	How? Communication channel	Description	Who? Target audience	Outcome	Status
RADOV start	Press release	Announcement of the start of RADOV, including a description of its aims.	Citizens	Outreach to media and public.	Delivered
Article "EURATOM HORIZON EUROPE PROJECT COORDINATED BY INCT APPROVED FOR FUNDING!"	Press release	Published in Progress in Nuclear Technology". The article contains essential information on the project.	Citizens, Research communities	Increase of the project visibility.	Delivered
Website post http://www.ichtj.waw.pl/drupal_eng/?q=node/198	Social media	Information on the INCT webpage and Facebook fanpage on project acceptance for funding including project summary and	Citizens, Research communities	Increase of the project visibility.	Delivered

		list of participants.			
Website post https://www.kpk.gov.pl/hydrozelowe-opatrunki-z-kurzzych-jaj-ichtj-koordynuje-projekt-euratom	Social media	National Contact Point website. Information on the project.	Citizens, Research communities	Increase of the project visibility.	Delivered
Website post https://c2tn.tecnico.ulisboa.pt/radov/	Social media	Information on the C2TN webpage about project scope	Citizens, Research communities	Increase of the project visibility.	Delivered
RADOV project	Event	Inclusion of RADOV in several presentations in IFAST EU project.	Research communities	Outreach to scientific community	Delivered
Website post http://www.ichtj.waw.pl/drupal/?q=node/1323	Social media	Information on the INCT webpage and Facebook fanpage, Report on RADOV 12M Annual Meeting	Citizens, Research communities	Increase of the project visibility.	Delivered
Website post http://www.ichtj.waw.pl/drupal_eng/?q=node/200	Social media	Report on RADOV Kick-off Meeting.	Citizens, Research communities	Increase of the project visibility.	Delivered
Article "RADOV 12M Annual Meeting" http://www.ichtj.waw.pl/ptj/Pliki/ptj2023no4.pdf	Press release	Published in "Progress in Nuclear Technology". The article contains report on RADOV 12M Annual Meeting	Citizens, Research communities	Increase of the project visibility.	Delivered
Article "RADOV Kick-off Meeting" http://www.ichtj.waw.pl/ptj/Pliki/ptj2023no1.pdf	Press release	Published in "Progress in Nuclear Technology". The article contains report	Citizens, Research communities	Increase of the project visibility.	Delivered

		on RADOV Kick-off Meeting			
--	--	---------------------------	--	--	--

PLANNED

Communication activity name	How? Communication channel	Description	Who? Target audience	Outcome	Status
RADOV Annual Meetings	Social media	Information on the INCT webpage and Facebook fanpage, Report on RADOV Annual Meetings	Citizens, Research communities	Outreach to media and public.	Planned
Articles on Progress in Nuclear Technology	Press release	Articles including reports on RADOV Annual Meetings will be published in Progress in Nuclear Technology	Citizens, Research communities	Increase of the project visibility.	Planned

SUMMARY

Output	Number of planned activities	Number of delivered activities so far
Conference presentations	20	8
Publications	5	1
Press releases	10	4
Media posts	24	10
Thesis	1	0
Events	2	0

5 Conclusions and Outlook

The RADOV Communication and Dissemination Plan, described in this document, was developed within the overall RADOV Strategy following the basic objectives drafted in the RADOV proposal. A coherent set of procedures and advanced tools are in place. With the support of the Project Management Team, the RADOV members are becoming familiar with the setup procedures and tools and starting to use them. The Plan will naturally evolve and, in continuous coordination with the Project Management team as well as the Work Package Leaders and other members of RADOV, will provide and maintain a coherent set of procedures and tools to match any needs that may arise at the different stages in the lifetime of the project.

Annex 1: RADOV publication guidelines

The RADOV Publications Guidelines summarise the rules and necessary links that have been implemented to meet the directives of Horizon2020 and Horizon Europe on Open Access and Open Data. These rules are:

1. A machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication of all scientific publications related to the RADOV project must be published in one or more repositories for scientific publications. One of these must be the RADOV Zenodo repository:
<https://zenodo.org/communities/radov/?page=1&size=20>
2. The specification that all RADOV publications must acknowledge the support from the EU and Euratom and the text that should be used, including the grant agreement fund number, has been created.
3. RADOV members are also made aware that publications can be submitted to the European Commission Scientific Publishing Service of Open Research Europe, that provides a peer-reviewed venue, at no cost, compatible with open access policies:
<https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu>
4. “Gold standard” is preferred for peer-reviewed publications. However, it is also important that high impact journals in the appropriate subject areas are used. RADOV members are encouraged to use existing agreements between their institute and publishers to obtain “Gold Open Access”.
5. In addition to the mandatory Zenodo, there are examples of other “Green Open Access” repositories for self-archiving, such as ArXiv.org, inSpireHEP.net and JACOW. The accelerator community has a long tradition of publishing scientific results in conference proceedings. Therefore, RADOV will make use of JACOW, the Joint Accelerator Conferences Website (<http://jacow.org>) when appropriate. JACOW is an international collaboration that publishes the proceedings of international accelerator conferences, whereby all conferences agree to the policies and requirements for Open Access publication. At present JACOW hosts the proceedings of some 20 of the most popular accelerator conferences including major international conferences such as the “International Particle Accelerator Conference” (IPAC) and International Instrumentation Conference (IBIC).
6. Data, in particular, those used in publications, must also be made available in Zenodo. This is described in the RADOV Data Management Plan.